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Conceptual study of excessive Lavana rasa intake and its effects in Ayurveda

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ABSTRACT

The modern day lifestyle comes with a package of hectic schedules at work place; time bound activities, work stress, inadequate sleep, improper and unhealthy diet and irregular, meal timings and many more. Apart from all this above things, the present day lifestyle includes excessive intake of salt through food, sometimes directly and sometimes through various sources like preserved food, marinated food, sauces, salted food stuff like cheese, butter, dry fruits. The daily consumption of unnecessary and many times excessive salty food gradually leads to lifestyle disorders such as hypertension, obesity, diabetes, kidney diseases. In Ayurved samhitas, special concept of *Rasa* has been described and whole chapter is dedicated to it. The various tastes of food like sweet, sour, bitter have been described which are 6 in number and they have specific function and specific ill effects if consumed excessively. In this paper, an effort has been made to elaborate the concept of excessive salty food intake and their ill effects which are evident in present time.

Keywords : Lavana Rasa, Excessive, Atiyog, Food, Indriyopaghat, Sense organ

INTRODUCTION

The excessive salt intake and associated diseases are a matter of concern in this era. They are not only affecting elderly age group, but also young and middle age group. According to PAHO (Pan American Health Organization), largest number of diet related deaths are due to excessive salt intake.³ WHO (World Health Organization) recommends maximum of 5gm /day salt intake in adults. Excessive salt intake more than this, would result into various metabolic and lifestyle disorders. Ayurved Samhita contains special mention of Lavana rasa atiyog¹ (Excessive salt intake) and related symptoms. Modern day lifestyle includes such excessive salty food intake frequently and this is a very serious issue as it leads to increase in burden of non communicable diseases.

Aim and objective

1. To study the *Lavana rasa* concept in Ayurveda
2. To study the ill effects of the *Lavana Rasa* described in samhita on *Indriya* (sense organ).

Materials and methods

Primary data is collected from Ayurvedic samhitas, journals and articles.

Review of literature

Ayurved samhita describes 6 *rasas* or tastes, which are Madhura (sweet), *Amla* (sour), *Lavana* (salty), *Katu* (pungent), *Tikta* (bitter) and Kashaya (astringent).² Among these 6 *Rasas*, *Lavana Rasa* (salty taste) is essential for enhancing the taste of the food. It liquefies and clears the channels of the body that are called *srtotas*. Though the constitution is *panchbhautika* (with 5 elements –*Prithvi, Teja, Aapa, Vayu, Aakash*a), it mainly comprised of *Teja* (fire) and *Aapa* (water) element in it. *Saindhava* is said to be the best *Lavana* to be consumed according to Ayurved. ¹ The excessive intake of *Lavana Rasa* results into excessive thirst, heat, penetrating swelling, fainting, teeth falling, emulsifying Mans, wrinkling of skin, hair fall, hair graying,

Raktapitta, Vatarakta, Vicharchika (skin disorder), alopecia, obstructing function of male genital tract, *Indriyopaghat* means disability or impairment of sense organs. It may be in terms of hampering normal functions of sense organs. Special mention of avoiding over consumption of 3 elements is found in *Vimansthana* in Charaka samhita. Those 3 elements are *Pippali* (piper longum), *Kshara* (alkaline extract) and *Lavana Rasa* (salty element).¹ It is mentioned that excessive use of these above elements should be avoided. It is said that excessive *Lavana Rasa* consumption results in weakness, inability to work, fatigue. It results in loosening of tissues. By above mentioned literature it is clear that *Lavana Rasa* has many serious effects on body.

Observations

The below mentioned health hazards of excessive intake of *Lavana Rasa* has been described in Ayurveda. WHO (world Health Organization) considered this issue as a major health concern.

Images 1 and Image 2 showing daily foods served or prepared with use of salt causing excess salt intake in daily diet.

Image 1 - French fries

Image 2- Processed cheese

Table 1: Lavana Rasa – Mahabhoota constitution, function and excess use

<i>Mahabhoota constitution</i>	Function	<i>Atiyog Lakshana</i>
<i>Aapa</i>	<i>Deepana</i> (Improves hunger)	Premature graying of hair, baldness
	<i>Pachana</i> (Improves digestion)	skin wrinkles, Lacerations
Mahabhoota And	<i>Bhedana</i> (separating character)	<i>Raktapitta, Amlapitta, Vatarakta,</i>
	<i>Chhedana</i> (Breaking of bonds)	<i>Vicharchika</i>
<i>Teja</i> Mahabhoota	<i>Kledana</i> (keeping the site soggy)	<i>Visarpa</i> and other <i>Rakta vikaras</i>
	<i>Shukraghna</i> (Anaphrodisiac and or oligospermia)	(Various types skin diseases from acute to chronic)

WHO has declared World Salt Awareness Day or World Non Communicable Disease Day on 22 May. Increased consumption of salt is associated with hypertension, increased risk of heart diseases and other non communicable diseases. Globally there is need to establish national salt control program to create awareness against excessive salt intake.

Discussion

The lifestyle nowadays consists of high amounts of consumption of food stuff which contains higher amounts of salt, sodium in it. These food items like marinated food, salted dry fruits, salted bakery products, preservative based products etc. have excess amount of salt. Their consumption on large level over a consistently long period has huge impact on health and it would lead to serious health issues like non communicable diseases. Ayurveda has significant reference of excessive salt consumption and its ill effect on health quoting many symptoms like untimely hair graying, wrinkles on skin, rakta related diseases like Vatarakta, Raktapitta, skin diseases like Vicharchika, Mansa bhedana, Chhhedana are the symptoms

presenting through skin disorders and Indriyopaghata (Dis functioning of senses). The meaning of the word *Indriyopaghata* in dictionary in Lavana rasa Atiyoga leads to obstruction in *indriya karma*. *Indriya* is a unique Ayurvedic concept. There are 5 Indriyas (sense organs) mentioned in Ayurveda. They are *Jivha*, *Twacha*, *Shrotra*, *Netra* and *Nasa* (tongue, skin, ears, eyes and nose respectively).

The *indriya* is responsible for the *artha graham prakriya* i.e. it helps in understanding the expected meaning of the subject or situation. Excessive salt intake results in producing impairment or obstruction in normal functioning of *indriya*. It may lead to skin diseases, vision impairment, ear related problems like deafness and nose related issues.

Table 2 : Indriya, element, Aadhisthana, Indriya artha and Indriya buddhi

Indriyas (Name of 5 Indriyas)	Dravya (Basic ele- ment)	Adhshthana (Location)	Indriya Arthas (Sense objects)	Indriya Buddhi (Knowledge)
<i>Shrotra</i>	<i>Aakasha</i>	<i>Karnas</i> (2 Ears)	<i>Shabada</i> (sound)	<i>Shrotra Buddhi</i> (Knowledge of sound)
<i>Sparsha</i>	<i>Vayu</i>	<i>Twak</i> (Skin)	<i>Sparsha</i> (Touch)	<i>Sparsha Buddhi</i> (Knowledge of Touch)
<i>Chakshu</i>	<i>Agni</i>	<i>Netra</i> (2 Eyes)	<i>Roopa</i> (Sight)	<i>Roopa Buddhi</i> (Knowledge of Vision)
<i>Rasana</i>	<i>Jala</i>	<i>Jivha</i> (Tongue)	<i>Rasa</i> (Taste)	<i>Rasa Buddhi</i> (Knowledge of Taste)
<i>Ghrasana</i>	<i>Prithvi</i>	<i>Ghrana</i> (Nose)	<i>Gandha</i> (Smell)	<i>Gandha Buddhi</i> (Knowledge of smell)

The Charaka samhita has also mentioned 3 substances Pippli, Kshara and Lavana are not to be consumed in excess. It creates serious health issues and should be consumed in appropriate quantity.

Conclusion

From the above mentioned discussion, it is clear that there are significant health issues due to excess salt intake, which results in various non-communicable diseases. It is described in Ayurveda in detail and again same can be evident in today's lifestyle related issues. It can be managed by creating awareness and setting guidelines for monitoring use of salt in diet.

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